

DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION OF A TEACHING AND LEARNING SEQUENCE CONCERNING THE MOON'S APPARENT MOVEMENT

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Abstract: The present study focuses on the planning, implementation and evaluation of a teaching and learning sequence regarding the Moon's apparent movement. The main aim of the sequence was to effectively teach the Moon's revolution around the Earth within a synodic month. A key point for the design of the sequence was to deal with the students' alternative idea that the Moon rises every day at the same time, which is imposed by the widely spread, erroneous belief that the Moon is always visible at night. The implementation of the sequence with K-5 students showed that the majority managed to successfully "construct" knowledge based on key concepts of the Moon's revolution around the Earth.

Keywords: Astronomy education, Moon' apparent movement, students' ideas

INTRODUCTION

In the past three decades many researchers have investigated children's and adults' ideas of several astronomical phenomena (Bailey & Slater, 2004). Some of these studies concerned phenomena of the Moon, such as its appearance (Venville, Luisell & Wilhelm, 2012), Moon-phases (Trundle, Atwood & Christopher, 2007; Parker & Heywood 1998), the "dark" side of the Moon (Dove, 2002; Trumper, 2001), tides (Taylor, Barker & Jones, 2003; Bisard, Aron, Francek & Nelson, 1994) and lunar eclipses (Bekiroglou, 2007; Barnett & Morran, 2002).

Students' ideas regarding the Moon's apparent movement have been recorded mainly as a means of examining the phenomenological foundation of the phenomenon (Plummer, 2009; Bekiroglou, 2007; Sharp, 1996; Mant & Summers, 1993). Among these ideas, the most frequently met are: a) the Moon is motionless; b) the Moon is invisible during daytime; c) the Moon rises every day at the same time.

As far as the interpretive mechanisms of the Moon's apparent movement are concerned, Starakis & Halkia (2010 a) have showed that 5th and 6th grade students' idea that the Moon is always visible at night has led them to believe that: a) the period of the Moon's apparent movement is 24-hour, and b) the Sun and the Moon are always at opposite sides of the Earth. Thus, while students are aware of the Moon's presence in the sky, they are not aware of the complexity of the relevant phenomenon: that the period of the Moon's apparent movement in the sky is not 24-hour, but is caused by the revolution of the Moon around the Earth and, at the same time, by the rotation of the Earth around its axis.

To overcome these ideas, a good starting point is to help students realize that each day the Moon appears in the sky with a 50 minute delay.

THE APPARENT MOVEMENT OF THE MOON (SCIENTIFIC MODEL)

A systematic observation of the Moon's apparent movement will help students to notice that the Moon rises every day with an approximate delay of fifty (50) minutes. According to the scientific model, this delay is due to a combination of two phenomena: the simultaneous *rotation of the Earth around its own axis once a day* and *the revolving of the Moon around the Earth within a synodic month*; both in the same direction (counterclockwise). Consequently, if the Moon did not revolve around the Earth, moonrise would happen every day at the same time. Moreover, due to the fact that the Earth spins counterclockwise, the Moon seems to rise in the east, and set in the west.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The present study is part of a research project concerning the teaching of the solar-terrestrial-lunar system's related movements. The theoretical framework of the research is based on the "educational reconstruction" model. According to this model, the analysis of the science content is strongly connected to empirical studies of students' conceptions and "learning pathways", and is targeted at developing instructional modules (Duit, Gropengiesser & Kattmann, 2005).

Following the steps of the "educational reconstruction" model, a preliminary analysis of the science content took place, followed by pilot studies of students' ideas about astronomical phenomena that are linked with the solar-terrestrial-lunar system's related movements (Starakis & Halkia 2010 a; Starakis & Halkia 2010 b). The combination of these steps led to:

- 1) the clarification of the scientific content:
 - a) The Earth's rotation around its own axis, lasting 24 hours,
 - b) The Moon's revolution around the Earth, lasting a synodic month,
 - c) The Earth's revolution around the Sun, lasting a year.

- 2) the design of a teaching and learning sequence, addressed to 5th grade pupils. It consists of three units with modular structure:
 - a) The Sun's apparent movement, b) The Moon's apparent movement, c) seasonal changes

The design of the sequence paved the way for the investigation of students' "learning pathways" concerning the solar-terrestrial-lunar system's related movements. Students' learning pathways were analysed according to the "teaching experiment" method, which combines typical interview and teaching elements (Komorek & Duit,

2004). The present work focuses on the planning, implementation and evaluation of the second unit of the sequence (The Moon's apparent movement).

THE RESEARCH

The research question

The research question is the following:

“Can 5th grade students attribute the Moon's apparent movement to the combination of the Earth's rotation around its own axis and the Moon's revolution around the Earth?”

The structure of a teaching and learning sequence regarding the Moon's apparent movement

The design of a sequence about the Moon's apparent movement presupposes that students, having completed the first unit of the main sequence (about the Sun's apparent movement), are already aware that the Earth rotates once a day around its own axis.

So, the main steps of the second unit (the Moon's apparent movement) are the following:

1st step

The aim of the first step is to help students:

- a) to actually observe the Moon's apparent movement in the sky.

This is very important, because while students are usually aware of the Moon's presence in the sky, they are not aware of its apparent movement. This is the main reason they have the idea that the Moon is motionless

- b) to express their ideas about the mechanism explaining Moon's apparent movement.

The means used to achieve this aim is a sequence of eight (8) stills showing the same frame of the sky shot at 25 minute intervals. In these stills, a set of objects (an existing electricity pole and wires) act as a concrete “frame of reference”, in relation to which tracing the Moon's position in the sky is easy. Thus, by observing these photographs, the Moon's apparent movement can be easily deduced.

The sequence of stills is presented to students, followed by the question:

“Why does the Moon appear to change position in the sky?”

Most students would be expected to ascribe the Moon's apparent movement exclusively to the Earth's rotation around its own axis.

2nd step

The aim of the second step is to help students express their ideas about the period of the Moon's apparent movement.

The means used to achieve this aim is a sequence of three images (one still followed by two sketches). Specifically: a) a still where the Moon appears to be on the top left in relation to the previously described "frame of reference" (an electricity pole and wires). The position of the Moon will act as a point of reference for the rest of the images; and b) two (2) identical paper sketches depicting only the "frame of reference" (the electricity pole and the wires). On these sketches students will be asked to draw the Moon in the positions they believe it would be (according to their ideas).

Actually, students are asked: 1) to carefully observe, on the first photograph, what is the position of the Moon in relation to the electricity pole and wires; 2) to draw on the second image (first sketch) the position of the Moon 24 hours later; 3) to draw on the third image (second sketch) the position of the Moon 48 hours later.

It is expected that, in both cases, most students will draw the Moon in exactly the same position as that shown in the first image (still), attributing a 24-hour period to the phenomenon.

3rd step

The aim of the third step is to help students confront their ideas about the period of the Moon's apparent movement.

The means used to achieve this aim is a sequence of three (3) stills (showing the same frame of the sky) shot at 24 hour-intervals. The stills reveal that, after 24 hours, the Moon has moved and appears to be in a different part of the sky.

4th step

The aim of the fourth step is to help students realize that the Moon revolves around the Earth.

The means used to achieve this aim are: a) a sequence of two (2) stills (showing the same frame of the sky) shot at 24 hour-intervals. The stills reveal that after 24 hours the Moon appears to be at a different position in the sky; b) a 24-hour periodicity floor standing clock (fig.1); and c) bodily-kinesthetic modelling of the Earth's and the Moon's movements. A child inside the clock (at the centre) would simulate the Earth, by reproducing the Earth's rotation around its own axis lasting 24 hours, while another child, outside the clock, would simulate the Moon.

By combining these means, students would be expected to realise that, within 24 hours, the Moon will "slightly" move around the Earth at a direction similar to the direction of the Earth's rotation around its own axis.

Figure 1. A 24-hour periodicity floor standing clock

5th step

The aim of the fifth step is to help students actually observe the daily delay of the Moon's appearance at the same part of the sky.

The means used to achieve this aim is a sequence of three (3) stills (showing the same frame of the sky) shot at intervals of 24 hours and 50 minutes. The stills depict the daily delay (50 minutes) of the Moon's appearance at the same part of the sky.

6th step

The aim of the sixth step is to help students realize that the Moon revolves around the Earth within 29,5 days.

The means used to achieve this aim are: a) a sequence of three (3) stills (showing the same frame of the sky) shot at intervals of 24 hours and 50 minutes. The stills depict the daily delay (50 minutes) of the Moon's appearance at the same part of the sky; and b) a 24-hour periodicity floor standing clock (with minutes' display) (fig.2)

Figure 2. Floor standing clock of 24-hour periodicity (with minutes' display)

By combining these means, students would be expected to divide 1440 by 50 in order to estimate the time the Moon needs to fully revolve around the Earth.

At the end of the sixth step students are expected to conclude that: *“The Moon’s apparent movement is due to the combination of the Earth’s rotation around its own axis once a day and the Moon’s revolving around the Earth within 29,5 days, both in the same direction “.*

Sample

The teaching sequence was implemented in 5 primary schools of Athens. 40 5th grade students (randomly chosen) took part in teaching experiments, in groups of 4 (2 groups from each school).

Data Collection

Pre/post interviews, as well as the video of the intervention /teaching experiments, were used for data collection. Post interviews were conducted a month after the teaching experiments. The Chi Square test was used for analysing pre/post interviews, while qualitative research methods were used for analyzing the intervention /teaching experiments (Erickson, 1998). One (1) student didn’t take part in the post interview.

RESULTS

Post interview analysis revealed that most students (30 out of 40 or 75%) were able to attribute the Moon’s apparent movement to the combination of the Earth’s rotation around its own axis and the Moon’s revolution around the Earth (category 2 in Table 1). Common ground among the answers was that the Moon moves daily only by a small portion of its orbit around the Earth. A characteristic dialogue deduced from the post interviews is presented below:

Student: In 24 hours, the Earth accomplishes one full rotation around its axis. At the same time the Moon moves a little.

Researcher: What do you mean with the phrase ‘the Moon moves a little’?

Student: The Moon revolves around the Earth. That is why we cannot see the Moon at the same place, every day at the same time.

Table 1

Students’ Answers (Before/After the Teaching Experiment), concerning the cause of the Moon’s apparent movement

Where can the Moon’s apparent movement be attributed?	Pre test	Post test
	N (%)	N (%)
1. Earth’s rotation around its own axis (the Moon is motionless)	12 (30)	2 (5)
2. Earth’s rotation around its own axis and the Moon’s revolving around the Earth	1 (2,5)	30 (75)

3. The Moon's apparent movement doesn't exist	12 (30)	0
4. The Moon's other movements (unclassified answers)	3 (7, 5)	0
5. Earth's revolving around the motionless Moon	3 (7, 5)	1 (2, 5)
6. Earth's revolving around the motionless Sun	1 (2, 5)	0
7. Incoherent answers	1 (2, 5)	3 (7, 5)

Note. Pearson chi-square: value=78,310, df=50, $p < 0,05$

Most students (22 out of 30 students of category 2 in table 1) mentioned at the post interview that the Moon's revolution around the Earth lasts almost a month, while the rest (8 out of 30 students of category 2 in table 1) refer to other time periods (e.g. 1 week, 10 days or half a year). Common ground among all these answers is students' reference that within a day the Moon performs only a small part of its revolution around the Earth.

For example, a students' characteristic answer was that:

"In 24 hours, the Moon makes a small step around the Earth"

Students also seem to have changed their views about the Sun-Earth-Moon systems' relative positions over a monthly span. The pre-interviews' analysis shows that the majority (82.5 %) claim that the Sun and the Moon are always at opposite sides of the Earth. The post-interviews' analysis revealed that this percentage dropped dramatically (15%) in favour of the scientific model (77.5 %) (Table 2).

Table 2

Most Frequently Encountered Answers, Among Students (Before/After the Teaching Experiment), Concerning Sun-Earth-Moon Systems' Relative Positions Over a Monthly Span

Sun-Earth-Moon Systems' Relative Positions Over a Monthly Span		Pre test N (%)	Post test N (%)
Sun and Moon at opposite sides		33 (82,5)	6 (15)
Scientific model		3 (7, 5)	31 (77,5)

Note. Pearson chi-square: value= 43,781, df=9, $p < 0,05$

The above results are also confirmed by the analysis of the students' dialogues during the intervention/teaching experiments. A crucial point in the procedure was that the observation of the stills which displayed a non-24-hour period of the phenomenon helped students to stop considering the Moon as motionless:

“As I can see, the Moon cannot stay still”

Moreover, bodily-kinesthetic modelling of the Earth's and the Moon's movements helped those students who were modelling the Earth, to almost spontaneously advise those students who were modelling the Moon, to slightly move towards the left:

“Make a step towards here (to the left) please”

The analysis also revealed that students found it hard to correlate the direction of the Moon's revolution around the Earth with the fact that the Moon appears daily at the same part of the sky with a 50 minute delay. This element was also present during post interviews, as only 13 students cited the precise direction, without providing further justification:

Researcher: The Moon's direction around the Earth is similar to the direction of the Earth's rotation around its own axis, according to your sketch.

Student: Yes. There must be a reason for this, but I cannot suggest any.

On the other hand, students' ideas about several phenomena of astronomy do not seem to have influenced their learning pathways crucially. Specifically:

i) The students' idea that the Moon is always visible at night didn't seem to have influenced their course to the “conclusion”. During the “teaching experiment”, when they found out that the Moon revolves around the Earth within 29,5 days, they were asked by the teacher/researcher if they could estimate how many days the Moon cannot be seen at midnight from a specific place on the Earth (e.g. Athens). Almost all the students replied correctly:

“Almost every fortnight”

The same conclusion could be drawn from the answers of the students in the post-interviews concerning the relative positions of the Sun-Moon-Earth over a monthly span (see Table 2).

The same can also be stated regarding the phenomenon of the lunar phases. The fact that we do not see the same portion of the Moon every day didn't seem to have

influenced students' explanations either during the "teaching experiment" or during the post-test interviews.

ii) The phenomenon that seemed to hinder the learning process of some students (5 out of 40) was "eclipses". These students considered that a solar eclipse should occur once a month (in the exact moment when the Moon passes between the Sun and the Earth), a fact that, from their point of view, didn't seem to be rational. A characteristic answer deduced from the post-interview, (concerning the frequency of the presence of the Moon between the Earth and the Sun) is presented below:

"Every 29 days, the Moon should pass between the Earth and the Sun, but this does not make sense, because then there should be a solar eclipse. On the other hand, I see a solar eclipse every few years...."

CONCLUSIONS

The present study presented the design, implementation and evaluation of a teaching and learning sequence, regarding the Moon's apparent movement.

The evaluation of the sequence revealed that the majority of the students can build bridges between a daily routine phenomenon (the Moon's apparent movement) and its interpretive mechanisms (the explanation according to the Earth-Moon systems' related movements).

The elements that should be re-examined when designing the sequence in a "full class scale" are: a) the connection between the direction of the Moon's revolving around the Earth, and the daily delay of the Moon's appearance at the same part of the sky and b) the handling of the students' misconceptions about the phenomenon of Moon's eclipses.

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